

THE IMPACT OF ACNE ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE AND PSYCHO-EMOTIONAL STATE OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT: The aim of this study was to assess the prevalence of acne among young people, to compare the level of awareness of acne among schoolchildren and students, and to analyze its impact on quality of life and psychosocial well-being. To achieve these objectives, a questionnaire was developed to assess clinical and anamnestic data as well as psychosocial aspects based on the Dermatologic Quality of Life Index (DLQI). The study was open, simple and short-term. A total of 614 participants, including 192 schoolchildren (13-16 years old) and 422 students (19-23 years old), were examined. Results showed that the prevalence of acne was similar in both age groups (43.8% and 46.4%, respectively), with no significant gender differences (46% in males vs. 44.8% in females). However, students showed a higher level of acne awareness compared to high school students (71.1 % vs. 40.6 %). Clinical symptoms such as itching, burning and pain were reported more frequently by female students. In addition, students with acne were 1.4 times more likely to experience decreased self-esteem compared to high school students. Girls in both groups were more prone to anxiety and depression, while boys showed higher levels of irritability. Acne was found to negatively affect leisure time, social interactions and personal life, with female students being the most affected. These results indicate the significant psychosocial burden of acne, emphasizing the need for a multidisciplinary approach to its treatment. Establishing collaboration between dermatologists and mental health professionals is crucial to address both the dermatologic and psychological aspects of acne, ultimately improving patients' overall well-being.

Keywords: Acne, prevalence, awareness, quality of life, psychosocial impact, mental health, treatment.

ВЛИЯНИЕ АКНЕ НА КАЧЕСТВО ЖИЗНИ И ПСИХОЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ МОЛОДЕЖИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: Целью данного исследования было оценить распространенность акне среди молодежи, сравнить уровень осведомленности школьников и студентов об акне, а также проанализировать его влияние на качество жизни и психосоциальное благополучие. Для достижения этих целей был разработан опросник для оценки клинических и анамнестических данных, а также психосоциальных аспектов, основанный на Дерматологическом индексе качества жизни (DLQI). Исследование было открытым, простым и краткосрочным. Всего было обследовано 614 участников, в том числе 192 школьника (13-16 лет) и 422 студента (19-23 года).

Результаты показали, что распространенность акне была одинаковой в обеих возрастных группах (43,8 и 46,4 % соответственно), без существенных гендерных различий (46 % у юношей против 44,8 % у девушек). Однако студенты продемонстрировали более высокий уровень осведомленности об акне по сравнению со школьниками (71,1 % против 40,6 %). Клинические симптомы, такие как зуд, жжение и боль, чаще отмечали студентки. Кроме того, студенты с акне в 1,4 раза чаще испытывали снижение самооценки по сравнению со школьниками. Девочки в обеих группах были более склонны к тревоге и депрессии, в то время как мальчики демонстрировали более высокий уровень раздражительности. Было установлено, что акне негативно влияет на досуг, социальные взаимодействия и личную жизнь, причем в наибольшей степени это касается студенток. Эти результаты свидетельствуют о значительном психосоциальном бремени акне, подчеркивая необходимость мультидисциплинарного подхода к его лечению. Установление сотрудничества между дерматологами и специалистами в области психического здоровья имеет решающее значение для решения как дерматологических, так и психологических аспектов акне, что в конечном итоге улучшает общее самочувствие пациентов.

Ключевые слова: Акне, распространенность, осведомленность, качество жизни, психосоциальное воздействие, психическое здоровье, лечение.

Introduction.

Acne is one of the most common chronic inflammatory skin diseases, primarily affecting adolescents and young adults. It is characterized by the formation of comedones, papules, pustules, and, in severe cases, nodules and scars. The disease develops due to the increased production of sebum, follicular hyperkeratosis, bacterial colonization by *Cutibacterium acnes*, and inflammatory reactions.

Despite being a non-life-threatening condition, acne significantly impacts patients' quality of life. Its visible manifestations often lead to emotional distress, decreased self-esteem, social withdrawal, and, in some cases, depression or anxiety disorders. Studies have shown that individuals with acne experience higher levels of psychological distress compared to those without dermatological conditions.

While genetic predisposition plays a key role in acne development, environmental factors, including diet, stress, and hormonal fluctuations, can also contribute to its severity. The effectiveness of acne treatment depends on timely diagnosis and an individualized approach that may include topical and systemic therapy, lifestyle modifications, and psychological support.

Given the increasing prevalence of acne among young people and its significant psychosocial burden, studying its impact on different age groups is highly relevant. This research aims to assess the prevalence of acne, compare the awareness levels of schoolchildren and students, and analyze the impact of acne on their quality of life and psychological well-being.

Purpose of the study. The aim of the work is to estimate the prevalence of acne among young adults, to compare the level of awareness of schoolchildren and students about acne, and to analyze the impact of the disease on the quality of life and psychosocial state of representatives of different age groups.

Objectives of the study. A questionnaire was developed for the study, including questions to assess clinical and anamnestic data, as well as psychosocial aspects of the disease based on the index of dermatologic quality of life. The study included 614 participants: schoolchildren (13-16 years old) and

students (19-23 years old). Data were collected through an anonymous online survey, paper questionnaire and work in dormitories.

Results of the study. The study revealed that the prevalence of acne among schoolchildren (13-16 years old) and students (19-23 years old) was 43.8% and 46.4%, respectively, indicating no significant differences between age groups. Gender differences were also found to be insignificant: acne was reported in 46% of males and 44.8% of females.

When acne awareness was analyzed, it was found that students were significantly better informed about the disease than schoolchildren: 71.1% vs. 40.6%, respectively. Among students, the level of awareness was higher in girls (77.6%) than in boys (60.7%), whereas among schoolchildren the rate was 48.6% in girls and 30.6% in boys.

As for clinical manifestations, itching, burning and soreness of the skin were more frequently reported by girls, especially in the student group (84.4% vs. 75.7% in boys). Among schoolchildren, these symptoms were recorded in 70.2% of respondents, with girls (77.3%) also complaining about them more often than boys (62.5%).

Analysis of psycho-emotional impact showed that students with acne 1.4 times more often reported a decrease in self-esteem compared to schoolchildren (77% vs. 53.5%). Girls were particularly vulnerable: among female students, 93.4% reported a deterioration in self-esteem, while among schoolgirls this figure amounted to 50%.

Anxiety due to acne was experienced by 32.1% of schoolchildren and 46% of students. Girls were more susceptible to anxiety: among schoolgirls this indicator amounted to 54.5%, among students - 63.1%. Depression due to acne was noted by 1.2% of schoolgirls and 8.7% of students, and among them the majority were also girls (13.1%).

Irritability as a response to the presence of acne was more frequently noted in boys (40% of schoolchildren and 57% of students), while this indicator was lower in girls (22.7% and 20.5%, respectively).

Acne affected the social activity and leisure time of 21.4% of schoolchildren and 34.2% of students, with a stronger impact among girls (31.8% of schoolgirls and 46.7% of students). Personal life was also affected for 29.8% of schoolchildren and 31.1% of students, among whom girls were again the most vulnerable (50% of schoolgirls and 40.2% of students).

Thus, the findings emphasize the need for a comprehensive approach to acne treatment, taking into account not only dermatological but also psycho-emotional aspects of the disease.

Conclusions. The study showed that the prevalence of acne among schoolchildren (13-16 years old) and students (19-23 years old) is comparable (43.8% and 46.4%, respectively), and gender differences in the incidence of the disease are minimal. However, students turned out to be more aware of the acne problem compared to schoolchildren (71.1% vs. 40.6%).

Analysis of the psychoemotional state showed that acne has a significant impact on the quality of life of young people. Girls more often reported pronounced clinical manifestations (itching, burning, soreness) and were also more prone to anxiety, depression and lower self-esteem. It was found that students with acne were 1.4 times more likely to report worsening self-esteem compared to schoolchildren (77% vs. 53.5%). The greatest vulnerability to psycho-emotional disorders was demonstrated by girls aged 19-23 years, for whom acne became a significant factor affecting personal life, leisure and social activity.

Thus, acne is not only a dermatologic but also a psychosocial problem that requires a comprehensive approach to treatment. It is important to organize interaction between dermatologists and mental health specialists for timely diagnosis and correction of psychoemotional disorders in patients with acne.

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